

Ternary Complexes : Equilibrium Study of the Mixed Complexes of Uranyl Ion with Dipicolinic Acid as a Primary Ligand and Some Dicarboxylic Acids as Secondary Ligands*

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A pH titration method has been used to determine the equilibrium constants for the mixed-ligand systems of uranyl ion with dipicolinic acid as primary ligand and malonic, succinic, itaconic, glutaric, adipic, thiomalic, thiodiglycolic and thiodipropionic acids as secondary ligands at 30° and ionic strength $\mu=0.1M$ (NaClO_4). Dipicolinic, malonic and glutaric acids form 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 chelates with uranyl ion while remaining acids form only 1 : 1 chelate in the pH range 2.5-5.0. It is observed that the coordination of UO_2^{2+} with thiodicarboxylic takes place through oxygens of carboxylate groups, whereas dipicolinic acid bonds through N-O donor atoms filling the equatorial position of coordination sphere of the metal ion. The preferential formation of ternary complexes over binary ones have been discussed on the basis of ring size of chelating acid, basicity of the secondary ligands and the distribution of simple and mixed species present as a function of pH.

DURING recent years intensive investigations have been carried out on the mixed-ligand systems of metal ion with biologically important ligands¹⁻⁴. Recently Gergely and Nagypal⁵ have studied the mixed-ligand complexes of Cu^{2+} -dipeptide-amino acids. Although a considerable number of complexes of UO_2^{2+} -carboxylate with amino acids^{6,7}, dicarboxylic^{8,9} and thiodicarboxylic¹⁰ acids have been investigated previously, no work has been published on UO_2^{2+} pyridine dicarboxylic-thiodicarboxylic acids. However, it is surprising that a single system of UO_2^{2+} -dipicolinic-thiodicarboxylic acid has not been studied to date. In view of the above, the present work is carried out to examine the complexing ability of thiodicarboxylic acids with UO_2^{2+} -dipicolinic binary complexes and to discuss the preferential formation of ternary complexes over binary ones.

Experimental

The chemicals used were Fluka, purum products. The concentrations of metal ion was estimated by using the standard procedure¹¹. Details of other reagents are given in an earlier paper¹². All pH measurements were made with a Elico digital pH meter model L 1-120 (No. 1275) with a glass and calomel electrode assembly at $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$ and an ionic strength 0.1 M (NaClO_4). The accuracy of pH meter was ± 0.01 pH units. The pH meter was

standardized before each titration by potassium hydrogen phthalate buffer with pH value of 4.01 at 30°. A value of 0.83 for the activity coefficient of 0.1 M (H^+) was used in conversion of pH values to hydrogen ion concentrations¹³. A steady stream of nitrogen gas, freed from carbon dioxide, was passed through the solution during titration.

Results and Discussion

Acid dissociation constants of the ligands and stability constants of simple uranyl complexes were evaluated by the method of Irving and Rossotti¹⁴. The method of calculation of equilibrium constant of ternary complexes, used in the present work has been developed by Ramamoorthy and Manning¹⁵. The equilibrium constant K_{MXY} for the reaction :

$$K_{\text{MXY}} = \frac{[\text{MXY}][\text{H}]^2}{[\text{MY}][\text{H}_2\text{X}]} \quad \dots (2)$$

is calculated. According to this method the concentrations of total metal ion (C_M), ligand (C_X), ligand (C_Y) and hydrogen ion (C_H) are distributed as follows :

$$C_M = [\text{M}] + [\text{MX}] + [\text{MX}_2] + [\text{MY}] + [\text{MY}_2] + [\text{MXY}] \quad \dots (3)$$

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$$C_x = [X] + [HX] + [H_2X] + [MX] + 2[MX_2] + [MXY] \quad \dots (4)$$

$$C_y = [Y] + [HY] + [H_2Y] + [MY] + 2[MY_2] + [MXY] \quad \dots (5)$$

and

$$C_H = [H] + [HX] + 2[H_2X] + [HY] + 2[H_2Y] \quad \dots (6)$$

The total available hydrogen ions at any point in the titration curve is given by the expression :

$$C_H = 2C_x + 2C_y + P - C_B \quad \dots (7)$$

where P is the total concentration of perchloric acid, C_H = total titrable hydrogen ion and C_B = NaOH added. This method is for the calculations of equilibrium constants for the mixed ligand complexes involving two dibasic ligand acids which

$$M^{2+} = \frac{[H_2X]\{1 + K_{1X}/[H] + K_{1X}K_{2X}/[H]^2\} + C_M - C_x}{1 + [H_2Y]K_{MY_1}K_{1Y}K_{2Y}/[H]^2 + [H_2Y]^2K_{MY_1}K_{MY_2}(K_{1Y}K_{2Y})^2/[H]^4} - [H_2X]^2K_{MY_1}K_{MX_2}(K_{1X}K_{2X})^2/[H]^4 \quad \dots (10)$$

$$M^{2+} = \frac{[H_2Y]\{1 + K_{1Y}/[H] + K_{1Y}K_{2Y}/[H]^2\} + C_M - C_y}{1 + [H_2X]K_{MX_1}K_{1X}K_{2X}/[H]^2 + [H_2X]^2K_{MX_1}K_{MX_2}(K_{1X}K_{2X})^2/[H]^4} - [H_2Y]^2K_{MY_1}K_{MY_2}(K_{1Y}K_{2Y})^2/[H]^4 \quad \dots (11)$$

form 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 binary complexes with the metal ion individually.

From the above equation and dissociation constants of ligands, K_{1X} , K_{2X} , K_{1Y} and K_{2Y} , we get

$$[H_2X] = a - b[H_2Y] \quad \dots (8)$$

where

$$a = \frac{2C_x + 2C_y + P - C_B - [H]}{2 + K_{1X}/[H]} \quad \dots (8a)$$

and

$$b = \frac{2 + K_{1Y}/[H]}{2 + K_{1X}/[H]} \quad \dots (8b)$$

$[H_2Y]$ is calculated from a third degree equation

$$A_1[H_2Y]^3 + A_2[H_2Y]^2 + A_3[H_2Y] + A_4 = 0 \quad \dots (9)$$

where

$$A_1 = -b^3d_xf_x + bd_xf_y - d_yf_y + b^2d_yf_x,$$

$$A_2 = b^2d_xe_x + 3ab^2d_xf_x - ad_xf_y - b^2c'_xf_x + c'_yf_y - d_ye_y - 2abd_yf_x + c'_yf_y - b^2c'_yf_x,$$

$$A_3 = -bd_x - 2abd_xe_x - 3a^2bd_xf_x + bc'_xe_x + 2abc'_xf_x - d_y + a^2d_yf_x + c'_ye_y + 2abc'_yf_x,$$

and

$$A_4 = ad_x + a^2d_xe_x + a^2d_xf_x - c'_x - ac'_xe_x - a^2c'_xf_x + c'_y - a^2c'_yf_x,$$

where in turn,

$$C'_x = C_x - C_M \quad C'_y = C_y - C_M$$

$$d_x = 1 + K_{1X}/[H] + K_{1X}K_{2X}/[H]^2,$$

$$d_y = 1 + K_{1Y}/[H] + K_{1Y}K_{2Y}/[H]^2,$$

$$e_x = K_{MX_1}K_{1X}K_{2X}/[H]^2,$$

$$e_y = K_{MY_1}K_{1Y}K_{2Y}/[H]^2,$$

$$f_x = K_{MX_1}K_{MX_2}(K_{1X}K_{2X})^2/[H]^4, \text{ and}$$

$$f_y = K_{MY_1}K_{MY_2}(K_{1Y}K_{2Y})^2/[H]^4,$$

where, K_{1X} , K_{2X} , K_{1Y} and K_{2Y} are first and second dissociation constants of ligand (X) and (Y) respectively and K_{MX_1} , K_{MX_2} , K_{MY_1} and K_{MY_2} are the stability constants of simple complexes from equation (9) was obtained by equating equations (10) and (11) :

resulting from the equations (6)-(13) and those for the concentrations of simple complexes MX_1 , MX_2 , MY_1 and MY_2 .

The IBM 370/155-II electronic computer was used to calculate :

(i) $[H_2Y]$ from equation (9)

(ii) $[H_2X]$ from equation (8)

(iii) $[M^{2+}]$ from M^{2+}

$$= \frac{d_x[H_2X] + d_y[H_2Y] - C'_x - C'_y}{2 + e_x[H_2X] + e_y[H_2Y]} \quad \dots (12)$$

(iv) $[MX] = K_{MX_1}K_{1X}K_{2X}[M^{2+}][H_2X]/[H]^2 \quad \dots (13)$

(v) $[MX_2] = K_{MX_1}K_{MX_2}[M^{2+}]/(K_{1X}K_{2X}[H_2X])^2/[H]^4 \quad \dots (14)$

(vi) $[MY] = K_{MY_1}K_{1Y}K_{2Y}[M^{2+}][H_2Y]/[H]^2 \quad \dots (15)$

(vii) $[MY_2] = K_{MY_1}K_{MY_2}[M^{2+}]/(K_{1Y}K_{2Y}[H_2Y])^2/[H]^4 \quad \dots (16)$

(viii) $[MXY] = C_M - [M^{2+}] - [MX] - [MX_2] - [MY] - [MY_2] \quad \dots (17)$

and

(ix) $K_{MXY} = [MXY][H]^2/[MY][H_2X]$

The equilibrium constants β_{XY} , K_{DXY} , K_{2XY} and K_{2YX} were obtained from K_{MXY} using equations

(18)-(21), namely,

$$\beta_{XY} = K(M + X + Y \rightleftharpoons MXY) = K_{MXY}K_{MY_1}/K_1XK_2X \quad \dots (18)$$

$$K_{DXY} = K(MX_2 + MY_2 \rightleftharpoons 2MXY) = (\beta_{XY})^2 / (K_{MX_1}K_{MX_2}K_{MY_1}K_{MY_2}) \quad \dots (19)$$

$$K_{2XY} = K(MX + Y \rightleftharpoons MXY) = K_{MXY}K_{MY_1}/K_1XK_2XK_{MX_1} = \beta_{XY}/K_{MX_1} \quad \dots (20)$$

and

$$K_{2YX} = K(MY + X \rightleftharpoons MXY) = K_{MXY}/K_1XK_2X = \beta_{XY}/K_{MY_1} \quad \dots (21)$$

The concentration of the species H_2Y , H_2X , M^{2+} , MX , MY , MY_2^{2-} and MXY^{2-} were calculated by using IBM 370/155 II-electronic computer at Indian Institute of Technology, Madras. Calculated concentration of the species present and their corresponding equilibrium constants for the systems UO_2^{2+} -dipicolinic-thiodicarboxylic acids are given in Fig. 1. and Tables 1 and 2. The average equilibrium constants for other systems are given in Table 3.

The stability of ternary complexes is given by $\Delta \log K$ values,

$$\Delta \log K = \log K_{MX}^{MX} - \log K_{MY}^M = \log K_{MYX}^{MY} - \log K_{MX}^M,$$

one would expect the negative $\Delta \log K$ for the formation of ternary complexes^{1,6,4}. It is also

reported in the literature that positive $\Delta \log K$ values for mixed ligand complexes indicating thereby the equilibrium $MX + MY \rightleftharpoons MXY^{2-} + M^{2+}$ is more on right side⁴. Another method of characterization of ternary complexes is by the use of constants

Fig. 1. Distribution of various species present in the ternary uranyl ion-dipicolinic (H_2Y)-thiomalic (H_2X) acid system as a function of pH. M^{2+} =uranyl ion free, MX =uranyl ion-thiomalic acid, MY =uranyl ion-dipicolinic acid, MY_2^{2-} =uranyl ion (dipicolinic acid), and MXY^{2-} =uranyl ion-thiomalic-dipicolinic acid. $\mu=0.1M$ ($NaClO_4$), Temp. $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$, $C_M=C_X=C_Y=2.0 \times 10^{-3}M$.

TABLE 1— UO_2^{2+} -DIPICOLINIC (H_2Y)-THIODIGLYCOLIC (H_2X) ACID SYSTEM
CALCULATED CONCENTRATIONS OF M^{2+} , H_2Y , H_2X AND SIMPLE AND MIXED SPECIES

pH	$C_M=C_X=C_Y$ $\mu=0.1M(NaClO_4)$ Temp. $30 \pm 0.1^\circ C$									
	$[H^+] \times 10^4$	$C_B \times 10^3$	$[H_2X] \times 10^4$	$[H_2Y] \times 10^6$	$[M^{2+}] \times 10^4$	$[MY] \times 10^4$	$[MY_2^{2-}] \times 10^4$	$[MX] \times 10^4$	$[MXY^{2-}] \times 10^4$	
3.80	1.906	13.120	1.725	1.667	3.084	4.469	4.088	1.771	5.935	
3.85	1.699	13.276	1.656	1.427	2.755	4.306	4.247	1.622	6.418	
3.90	1.514	13.347	1.429	1.089	2.709	4.068	3.857	1.756	6.944	
3.95	1.349	13.422	1.228	0.884	2.598	3.985	3.856	1.830	7.063	
4.00	1.203	13.498	1.047	0.717	2.483	3.889	3.845	1.884	7.229	
4.05	1.072	13.573	0.884	0.579	2.366	3.772	3.795	1.915	7.477	
4.10	0.955	13.648	0.739	0.468	2.246	3.640	3.722	1.917	7.796	
4.15	0.851	13.724	0.611	0.376	2.124	3.485	3.609	1.980	8.211	
4.20	0.759	13.799	0.498	0.315	1.997	3.307	3.455	1.829	8.729	

TABLE 2—EQUILIBRIUM CONSTANTS OF UO_2^{2+} -DIPICOLINIC (H_2Y)-THIODIGLYCOLIC (H_2X) ACID SYSTEM

$[H^+] \times 10^4$	$C_M=C_X=C_Y$ $\mu=0.1M(NaClO_4)$ Temp. $30 \pm 0.1^\circ C$				
	K_{MXY}	β_{XY}	K_{DXY}	K_{MX}^{MX}	K_{MY}^{MY}
1.906	-1.136	9.284	0.564	5.804	3.794
1.699	-1.094	9.272	0.602	5.842	3.833
1.514	-1.079	9.290	0.620	5.860	3.850
1.349	-1.099	9.271	0.601	5.841	3.831
1.202	-1.111	9.261	0.589	5.829	3.819
1.072	-1.111	9.259	0.589	5.829	3.819
0.955	-1.100	9.269	0.599	5.839	3.829
0.851	-1.077	9.293	0.623	5.863	3.853
0.759	-1.040	9.300	0.660	5.900	3.890
Average	-1.094	9.275 ± 0.03	0.605 ± 0.03	5.845 ± 0.03	3.835 ± 0.03

TABLE 3—LOGARITHMS OF EQUILIBRIUM CONSTANTS OF TERNARY COMPLEXES OF UO_2^{2+} -DIPICOLINIC*
 (H_2Y)-SECONDARY (H_2X) LIGAND ACIDS

Systems/acid	$\mu = 0.1M(\text{NaClO}_4)$		Temp. $30 \pm 0.1^\circ\text{C}$				Alog K
	β_{XY}	K_{DXY}	$K_{\text{MX}}^{\text{MX}}$	$K_{\text{MY}}^{\text{MY}}$	K_{MX}^{M}	$K_{\text{MX}_2}^{\text{MX}}$	
Dipicolinic-malonic	11.15 ± 0.02	2.67 ^c	5.59	5.71	5.56	3.80	+0.15
Dipicolinic-succinic	9.61 ± 0.03	-0.12 ^b	5.12	4.16	4.48	—	-0.31
Dipicolinic-itaconic	9.94 ± 0.02	-0.16 ^b	5.08	4.50	4.86	—	-0.36
Dipicolinic-glutaric	11.07 ± 0.01	5.07 ^c	7.37	5.63	3.70	2.69	+1.93
Dipicolinic-adipic	9.20 ± 0.03	-0.12 ^b	5.12	3.76	4.08	—	-0.32
Dipicolinic-thiomalic	9.90 ± 0.02	0.96 ^b	6.20	4.46	3.70	—	+0.76
Dipicolinic-thiodiglycolic	9.27 ± 0.03	0.60 ^b	5.84	3.83	3.43	—	+0.40
Dipicolinic-thiodipropionic	9.72 ± 0.01	0.44 ^b	5.68	4.28	4.04	—	+0.24

* $K_{\text{MY}}^{\text{M}} = 5.44$; $K_{\text{MY}_2}^{\text{MY}} = 5.24$.

c = $\text{MX}_2^{2-} + \text{MY}_2^{2-} \rightleftharpoons 2\text{MXY}^{2-}$.

b = $\text{MX}_2^{2-} + \text{MY} \rightleftharpoons \text{MXY}^{2-} + \text{MX}$, or $\text{MX} + \text{MY}_2^{2-} \rightleftharpoons \text{MXY}^{2-} + \text{MY}$.

$\text{MX}_2^{2-} + \text{MY}_2^{2-} \rightleftharpoons 2\text{MXY}^{2-}$. The value of K_{DXY} expected on statistical basis¹⁷ is 0.6 log units.

In the present investigation dipicolinic acid forms 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 chelates while thiomalic, thiodiglycolic, thiodipropionic acids form only 1 : 1 complexes with uranyl ion in the pH range 2.5 to 5.0. Dipicolinic acid can be considered as primary ligand and thiomalic, thiodiglycolic, thiodipropionic which can respectively form seven, eight and ten membered rings, as the secondary ligands. The coordination of UO_2^{2+} with dipicolinic acid can take place through oxygen of carboxylate group and nitrogen of pyridine ring, filling the equatorial positions of the coordination sphere and acid must be tridentate, in agreement with the earlier findings of Edward *et al*¹⁸ and Rayford¹⁹. In our earlier studies of mixed-ligand complexes, the tridentate nature of dipicolinic acid with transition metal ions, particularly copper ion, has been explained on the basis of structural rearrangement in the mixed-complex²⁰. In dipicolinic acid, the chelate ring size is smaller than in quinolinic acid. The difference in log K_1 and log K_2 indicates the formation of 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 chelate formation as almost simultaneous. The chelate ring in the case of UO_2^{2+} -thiomalic acid is found to be stabilized by the neutral sulphur atom while these UO_2^{2+} -thiodiglycolic and UO_2^{2+} -thiodipropionic acid binary complex stabilities are in the expected order of magnitude as indicated by pK values.

The formation of MXY^{2-} for UO_2^{2+} -dipicolinic-thiodicarboxylic acid system is considerable around pH 2.6. The concentrations of MX and MY_2^{2-} are maximum at around pH 3.2 and 3.8 respectively. In all systems, MXY^{2-} curves show an initial fall, followed by a flat minima and then continuously increases with an increase in pH. The formation of MX starts from pH 3.0, increases up to pH 4.1 and then slowly decreases. As a consequence of this, there is an increase in the concentration of MXY^{2-} above pH 3.7, though it is almost constant in the

pH range 3.1-3.6. The formation of simple and mixed species could be represented by the reactions :

A perusal of all these graphs reveal a distinct difference in the MXY^{2-} curve of the UO_2^{2+} -dipicolinic-thiodipropionic with the MXY^{2-} curves of the remaining two systems. The reactions (2a and 2b) are favourable for formation of simple species while (3a) is favourable for MXY^{2-} up to pH 3.1. The formation of MXY^{2-} is also possible by the reactions :

and

These reactions can proceed to the right side when a sufficient amount of MX, MY and MY_2^{2-} are available. The circumstances for the formation of MXY^{2-} are from pH 3.1 and onwards. In addition to this, there is a decrease in the concentration of MXY^{2-} up to pH 3.1. The precise reactions of the changes in the concentrations of MXY^{2-} may be interpreted in the form of its formation equilibria

corresponding to the pH ranges and are as :

The potentiometric titration data revealed that three hydrogen ions are liberated during the mixed-ligand formation ; therefore, it is erroneously concluded that the formation of MXY^{2-} takes place by the above mentioned equilibria.

$\Delta \log K$ values (Table 3) exhibit the same trend as that of UO_2^{2+} -quinolinic-secondary ligands¹⁰ except in the case of UO_2^{2+} -dipicolinic-glutaric acid. The tendency of the mixed-ligand formation is the same in the case of UO_2^{2+} -dipicolinic-succinic, UO_2^{2+} -dipicolinic-itaconic and UO_2^{2+} -dipicolinic-adipic acid ; $\Delta \log K = -0.31, -0.36$ and -0.32 respectively. The value of $K_{DXY} > 0.6$ in UO_2^{2+} -dipicolinic-thiomalic acid system for both the equilibria indicates the additional stabilization of the chelate ring by the neutral sulphur atom in the ternary complex. This effect is greater in the ternary complex than in the corresponding binary one⁹. The reaction constants are higher than 0.6 for UO_2^{2+} -dipicolinic-thiomalic, UO_2^{2+} -dipicolinic-thiodiglycolic and a bit less for UO_2^{2+} -dipicolinic-thiodipropionic acid system. The higher stabilities of the ternary chelates in relation to the binary stabilities is seen in Fig. 1, where MXY^{2-} curve is always above that of MX. In UO_2^{2+} -dipicolinic-thiodipropionic, on the other hand, MXY^{2-} curve in the intermediate pH region drops below MX curve.

The significantly higher values, i.e. 2.67 and 5.07 of K_{DXY} for UO_2^{2+} -dipicolinic-malonic and UO_2^{2+} -dipicolinic-glutaric acid systems respectively accompanied by the higher stability of ternary complexes may be due to very low stabilities of 1 : 2 binary complexes of the secondary ligands. The values of K_{DXY} for the remaining systems for both the equilibria show destabilized nature of ternary complexes. A perusal of all these graphs reveal the concentrations of ternary complexes decrease with increase in pH in the initial stages.

The values of K_{MXY}^{MX} and $K_{MY_2}^{MY}$ indicate the preferential formation of ternary complexes, over the binary except for systems involving the secondary ligands, succinic, itaconic and adipic acids. A comparison of K_{MYX}^{MY} values with $K_{MX_2}^{MX}$ especially in the systems involving malonic and glutaric acid as secondary ligands reveals the preferential formation of corresponding ternary complexes over the binary ones. The order of K_{MYX}^{MY} with reference to the

secondary ligands is malonic > glutaric > thiomalic > itaconic > thiodipropionic > succinic > thiodiglycolic > adipic, in accordance with 1 : 1 binary stabilities of these ligands except thiomalic acid²¹.

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